

Rule against Double Jeopardy

Nitya Nand Pandey, Assistant Professor, Amity Law School, Amity University Rajasthan, Jaipur

ABSTRACT

There are total six fundamental rights provided by the Indian Constitution. Amongst these six rights, one is the "Rule against Double Jeopardy" guaranteed under Article 20 (2) of the Indian Constitution. Apart from the constitution, various statutes also provide this doctrine. The purpose of this Article is to study and discuss all these provisions related to this doctrine and their exceptions at a glance.

Keywords

Indian Constitution, Double Jeopardy,

INTRODUCTION

Rule against double jeopardy has got the place in Indian legal system. The term "Double Jeopardy" was originate from the term "*Autrefois Acquit* and *Autrefois Convict*" which are the French terms and literally meaning is "previously acquitted" and "previously convicted" respectively.

These two terms have their origin in the common law where they are accepted as the pleas of *autrefois acquit* and *autrefois convict* and these pleas have the effect that the trial cannot go ahead due to the special circumstances that these two pleas depict.

Actually a plea of *autrefois acquit* means that a person cannot be tried again for an offence for the reason that he has previously been acquitted in the same offence and such a plea can be taken or combined with plea of not guilty.

Similarly a plea of *autrefois convict* means that a person cannot be tried again for an offence for the reason that he has been previously been convicted in an offence and the same can be combined with the plea of not guilty.

However these two terms are jointly known as Doctrine of *Autrefois Acquit* and *Autrefois Convict*. Actually this doctrine in a way is the rule again double jeopardy.

Rule against double jeopardy means that a person cannot be tried for the same offence once again if he has been either convicted or acquitted in the trial relating to same offence.

Protection against double jeopardy has been provided by many countries as a constitutional right, India being one of them. The other countries include Canada, Israel, Mexico and U.S.

However we will analyze this Doctrine of *Autrefois Acquit* and *Autrefois Convict* in special reference to Indian context in the light of the Section 300 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, Art. 20(2) of Constitution of India and Section 40,41,42,43 of Indian Evidence Act, 1872.

CONSTITUTION

The Constitution of India has provided this protection as a fundamental right under the Article 20(2) which provides "***No person shall be prosecuted and punished for the same offence more than once***".

The same principle has been enacted in the section 26 of the General Clauses Act, 1897.

CRIMINAL PROCEDURE CODE, 1973

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 which is the major procedural law with regard to the criminal cases has incorporated this doctrine which has been provided in section 300 of this code.

Section 300.(1) : A person who has once been tried by a court of competent jurisdiction for an offence and convicted or acquitted of such offence shall, while such conviction or acquittal remains in force, not be liable to be tried again for the same offence, nor on the same facts for any other offence for which a different charge from the one made against him might have been made under sub section (1) of section 221, or for which he might have been convicted under sub section (2) thereof.

IMPORTANT INGREDIENTS

If any accused is charged for any offence on any fact and-

- I. The trial should be conducted
- II. Such trial should be conducted before competent Court
- III. Decision of acquittal or Conviction should be passed in such trial
- IV. The accused may be charged alternative U/S 221(1) or he might have been convicted U/S 221(2).

Then-

He is not liable to be tried again on the same facts for the same offence, and

He is not liable to be tried again, on the same facts for any other offence for which a alternative charges might have been framed U/S 221(1), or for which he might have been convicted U/S 221(2).

Exceptions:- Under the following condition the rule against double jeopardy will not applicable:-

(1) Incompetent Court

Where the first court was not competent

(2) Same Transaction

Where more than one act has been committed and that creates same transaction and they also create more than one offence, and accused was punished for the several offence of them, he may be tried for remain offence after the prior approval state government. i.e. Continuous Offences.

A person acquitted or convicted of any offence may be afterwards tried, with the consent of State Government, for any distinct offence for which a separate charge might have been against him at a former trial under sub section (1) of section 220.

(3) Consequences Arisen After the Decision

When any other consequences have been arisen after the decision of acquittal or conviction, the accused may be charge and tried for such consequences arisen.

For example, if the person has committed grievous hurt and also convicted for the same but after the decision

victim is no more due to such hurt, accused may be tried again for murder and also might be convicted for the same.

(4) Same Fact Creates More Than One Offence

If the same fact creates more than one offence and the previous court is not competent for trial of all offences, rest may be tried in another competent court.

For example, if the same act of accused falls the definition of theft and robbery and first was tried by the Magistrate first class then second i.e. robbery may be tried by Magistrate second class in separate trial.

(5) Discharge U/S 258

Where the proceeding has been stopped U/S 258 and the accused is discharged, he may be tried again for the same offence with the consent of the Court by which he was discharged or of any other Court to which the first mentioned court is subordinate.

(6) Offence under deferent Act

As per section 26 of the General Clauses Act 1897 Where any act is declared an Offence by two or more Act and accused is punished under one act then he may charged under other act and may also be punished.

(7) Conviction or Acquittal outside India

If any person is convicted or acquitted outside India for any offence, he may be charged and tried in India on same fact.

(8) Dismissal of Complaint

If the complaint is dismissed by the magistrate, the consequence of such dismissal is discharge. So the accuse in such matter may be tried again. Because the rule against double jeopardy does not apply in matter of discharge. It apply only when the accused is acquit or convict.

(9) Discharge of Accused

Rule mention in point (8) is also applicable here. So the accused discharged may be prosecute again.

CONCLUSION

The doctrine of Autrefois acquit and Autrefois convict has been included as a fundamental right in our Constitution, though the purview of the doctrine is narrower than in

other statutes like Cr.PC, General Clauses Act, and that in other countries like U.K, U.S. However it is clear that in such circumstances the Constitution shall prevail. To conclude it can be said that this doctrine is a safeguard and acts as valve against the unlawful prosecution of a person for the same offence for the second time.

REFERENCES Section 300, Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973

- [1] Ratanlal and Dhirajlal, The Code of Criminal Procedure
- [2] Kelkar,R.V, Criminal Procedure
- [3] Krishnamachari,V, Law of Evidence
- [4] Section 40, Indian Evidence Act, 1872